

TRANSPPOSITION OF WORD CATEGORIES IN UZBEK

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Annotation. Exclamation, imitation, and modal words are examples of separately derived terms. These words fall into the category of words that do not belong to either independent words or auxiliary words but that in some way share the traits of both groups. The word categories in Uzbek are transposed and discussed in this article.

Keywords: Uzbek language, word categories, transposition, literature, dictionary meaning, grammar, syntactic tasks.

Introduction. Today, higher philological education is entrusted with the task of in-depth study of issues related to the unique features of the Uzbek language and literature, historical progress, its current state and prospects, strengthening the effectiveness of scientific research work carried out in this regard, radically improving the quality of teaching of Uzbek Language and Literature in all branches of the educational system and training highly qualified personnel, it is also making new requirements for the education tool. When categorizing words, the following three aspects are considered:

- 1) whether a word expresses or does not represent a noun (dictionary) meaning and whether or not it is an answer to an interrogative;
- 2) whether a word has certain grammatical forms or not;
- 3) whether a word can perform a syntactic task in a sentence or not.

According to these characteristics, word categories are divided into three groups, as above. Being an answer to a certain interrogative, words that have a (lexical) meaning of the noun and come in the function of a sentence fragment are

considered independent words: verb, noun, adjective, number, pronoun and syllable are independent words. Words that do not respond to a specific interrogative, do not have the meaning of an adjective, but only represent a grammatical meaning, cannot perform a single syntactic task in a sentence are auxiliary words: auxiliary, connecting, loading auxiliary words. Auxiliary words perform tasks such as linking words and sentences, as well as loading additional meaning over them.

Word categories have been defined using the division of words into large separate grammatical groups. Words are placed grammatically opposite as lexemes or word forms. When words are grammatically contrasted as lexemes, they are treated as categorical or lexical-grammatical categories. However, when words are juxtaposed as word forms, the categories of the word modifier or form builder are defined. Classification categories include word categories, while form-making categories include number, agreement, ownership categories. Grammatical category not only classifies, but also embodies the grammatical form together with the grammatical meaning as a form-making category.

Word categories are large groups of words that are distinguished by their grammatical signs in this language. Words that fall into different word categories are characterized by their paradigm or syntactic function, and form the basis of this classification. Word categorization helps in the analysis of different units in the language. Word categories are classified, taking into account the grammatical features of vocabulary in the dictionary. However, in the classification, words in one group cannot be included in another group. Each word belongs to one, and cannot be included in another second or in several groups. If a word has signs that belong to two groups (word category), then the third indicates the presence of another group.

For example, with a horse, the adjective does not have a kind of sign. But quality and clarity can have the same character. When the adjective is a sign of a horse, rhubarb is a sign of action. The words that represent different jobs form a separate grammatical group, the verb. The classification of words is the result of the

separation of lexemes into lexical-grammatical groups. But this classification does not include the classification of word forms. For this reason, it is necessary to take into account that the marking taken as a basis for the classification is common to all forms of the word or specific to some of its forms. In particular, many languages have nouns, while verbs are inflected. But as a result of the fact that the adjective as a form of a word has a single verb and an adjective mark, a separate Word category is not distinguished, but is a paradigm inherent in one form of the verb.

Each classification is based on grammatical-morphological, syntactic and other signs. For example, in Chinese, Korean, Vietnamese, Khmer, Thai and other languages, the verb and adjective are much closer. For this reason, in Chinese, the adjective and verb form a separate predicative group, and both of them function syntactically as cross-sections and take the suffixes corresponding to the verb. The predicative is therefore a separate Word category in Chinese.

Groups of words can be viewed in terms of their use in different syntactic positions. Other words subordinate to each independent word interpret the place of application. Signs of words are elucidated by an in-depth study of their use in the text. Consequently, it is necessary to define the rules of their use, in which group of words each word is specific, in which other words you take the same. Each word category is characterized by its own semantic characters, but in the classification of word categories, semantic characters are not fundamental. Because there are words that are distinguished by their characteristic of the two-three word category.

For example, it is to a semantically separate process, and at the same time are distinguished by grammatical meaning, that is, the word yellowing denotes the sign of the adjective - thing, the name of the running - action (a form of the verb). Word derivatives are distinguished by morphological features. In particular, each word category has its own Affixes and word-making tools.

At the same time, when science and technology are developing dramatically, information and communication tools are progressing very rapidly, the pace of life

is incomparably accelerated, the learner can not only quickly master the knowledge that is being updated hourly, but also distinguish the most perfect from them, find the right one, the very sought-after one, quickly master the novelty, fully meet the requirements of the learner, even an inexperienced teacher is required to be perfect enough to overcome his shortcomings.

It is known that in a theoretical approach, the noun (denotative) Semantics of a lexeme is understood as the action/state in being, the object-object, the quantity, the character-character-giving, the nominating semantics. It directly privatizes each of these as an independent word category – verb "to call action/case" SEMAS, noun "to call thing-object", numeral "to call quantity", adjective and adverb "to call character" SEMAS. The question may arise whether the specific noun semen of each word category is absolute and constant, or whether the phenomenon of the displacement (transposition) of word categories between independent word categories applies to this?

Word-Series displacement-transposition refers to a word belonging to a given Word-series that has a specific noun, a semantic and grammatical marker specific to another word-series, by weakening the sentence of the task. In Turkic words, the word category is not strictly delimited from each other, they form a system in one whole in continuous communication. The parts of this system are inextricably linked with the words that stand at the stage of moving from one category to another, preserving the semantic-grammatical mark inherent in both rows, which, due to the law of dialectical logic (intermediate third), is evaluated as a word. As a result of progress in lexeme SEMAS, the interrelationship between independent words and their displacement into each other, the colloquial and lysonized appearance of displacement is distinguished. In colloquial migration, the colloquial colloquial meaning is expressed.

For instance points out that in existing grammars, the classificatory symbols of the number category are dates, the number of the subject, the order of the subject,

the answer to one of the interrogations of (how many), (how many), (nechanchi), the word of the noun category is freely associated with it, and the sentence mainly comes in the function of an adjective-determinant. A deviation as a numerical common grammatical meaning is observed in the cumulative number genealogy, which is part of the group of numerical lexical content.

Conclusion. So, it can be said that there is regular communication between the word category, which indicates that communication is a living process in the constant change, development of the language system. Therefore, the belonging of certain words to which category should be determined on the basis of appropriate research of their semantic, morphological and syntactic properties. This is one of the urgent tasks facing our linguistic system.

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